

far, and therefore a systematic chemical examination of its fruits, leaves and roots of this plant was undertaken.

Fruits :

Air-dried powder (1.5 kg) of the fruit was extracted successively with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), chloroform and methanol. The petroleum ether extract (36 g) was a semi-solid, a part (17 g) of which was chromatographed over silica gel (500 g). Elution with petroleum ether gave a hydrocarbon (200 mg), m.p. 64-7°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 960-2 840 (C-H stretch of alkanes) and 1 450 cm^{-1} (C-H bend of alkanes); m/e 436 (M^+) 421 ($M^+ - \text{CH}_3$), 407, 393, 379 and 365. It was identified as hentriacontane⁷.

Further elution with petroleum ether-benzene (7 : 3) gave a white solid (360 mg), m.p. 84-8°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400 (OH), 2 930, 2 860 and 1 465 cm^{-1} ; m/e 448 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 433 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O} + \text{CH}_3$), 419, 415 and 391. It was characterised as dotriacontanol⁷. The petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1) eluate yielded a solid (30 mg), m.p. 112-6°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400, 2 930, 2 860 and 1 475 cm^{-1} ; m/e 436 ($M^+ - \text{H}_2\text{O}$), 418 ($M^+ - 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$)^{1,2}, 404, 390, 376, 362 and 348-52. It indicated to be a C_{30} -straight-chain diol, and formed a diacetate, $\text{C}_{34}\text{H}_{68}\text{O}_4$, ν_{\max} 1 735 cm^{-1} . It appears to be 1,30-triacontanediol⁸.

The chloroform extract on similar chromatographic analysis yielded dotriacontanol in petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°)-benzene (4 : 1) eluate, while ethyl acetate eluate furnished a solid, m.p. 278-80° which responded to positive L.B. test for sterol. It was identified as β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside from m.m.p., co-tlc and co-ir studies with authentic sample.

Leaves :

Air-dried powder (1.0 kg) of the leaves was extracted successively with petroleum ether, chloroform, acetone and methanol in a Soxhlet apparatus. Concentrated petroleum ether extract on usual chromatographic resolution over silica gel afforded hentriacontane, dotriacontanol and β -sitosterol while no compound could be isolated from the chloroform extract.

Acetone extract on concentration deposited a solid which was crystallised as needless (2 g) from pyridine. The compound did not melt up to 350° and was insoluble in common organic solvents; λ_{\max} (MeOH) 255 and 362, (MeOH + NaOAc) 278 and 355, (MeOH + AlCl_3) 272 and 380 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 480, 1 720, 1 620, 1 580, 1 500 cm^{-1} ; δ (DMSO- d_6) 7.5 (s) and 3.5 (br, s, D_2O exchangeable, OH). The compound was identified as ellagic acid by comparison with the reported spectral data⁹. The mother-liquor (25 g) remaining after the separation of ellagic acid was chromatographed over silica gel (500 g), and the ethyl acetate-acetone (19 : 1) eluate afforded a yellow solid (60 mg), m.p. 306-11°, which gave positive ferric chloride test for phenolic compound. It was found to be identical with the authentic sample of quercetin in tlc, m.p., m.m.p. and ir spectrum.

Roots :

Powdered roots (550 g) were extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). On concentration, the extract gave a solid which was crystallised repeatedly from ethyl acetate-benzene to yield white plates (0.9 g), m.p. 306-11°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 400-3 100 (OH), 1 690 (C=O), 1 640 and 882 cm^{-1} (isopropylene group)⁴. It responded to L.B. test for triterpene and was identified as betulinic acid by comparison of its mass⁵ and pmr⁶ spectra with those reported in literature. The mother-liquor (6.0 g) remaining after the separation of solid on chromatographic analysis over silica gel (200 g) gave a white solid (40 mg), m.p. 204-9°. It was found to be identical in all respects (co-tlc, m.m.p., ir spectra) with the reference sample of lupeol.

References

1. E. RYHAGE and E. J. J. STENHAGEN, *Lipid Res.*, 1960, 1, 861.
2. A. KINMANN and C. WAKSELMAN, *Bull. Soc., Chim. Fr.*, 1967, 3, 937.
3. B. O. SOWEMINO, F. H. SEGELMAN, M. TINWA, H. WAGNER, G. J. PERSINOS and N. R. FRANSWORTH, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1973, 62, 1358.
4. L. J. BELLAMY, "Infrared Spectra of Complex Molecules", Methuen, London, 1964.
5. H. BUDZIKIEWICZ, J. M. WILSON and C. DJERRASSI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 85, 3698.
6. M. SHAMMA, R. E. GLICK and R. J. MAMMA, *Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 4512.
7. W. KARRER, "Konstitution und Vorkommen der organischen Pflanzenstoffe, Band 12", Birkhauser Verlag, Basel, 1958.
8. H. A. SZYMANSKI, "Interpreted IR Spectra", Plenum Press, Data Division, New York, 1966, Vol. II.

Extraction Studies of Ruthenium(III) and Platinum(IV) with *S*-Benzylthiocarbamate

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Manuscript received 16 April 1985, revised 14 April 1986,
accepted 23 April 1986

A number of spectrophotometric reagents are known for the determination of ruthenium and platinum. Many sulphur containing reagents are found to be good extractants for these two metals¹⁻⁸. But no attempt has yet been made to study the colour reaction of ruthenium or platinum with *S*-benzylthiocarbamate (BDTC). The present investigation describes BDTC as new sensitive spectrophotometric reagent for micro determination of Ru^{III} at pH 2 and Pt^{IV} at pH 0.3. The Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} complexes gave λ_{\max} at 425 and 352 nm, respectively. The composition and stability constants of the extractable species were determined.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ru and Pt were prepared by dissolving the corresponding chlorides (A.R.) in HCl and standardised by the usual method^{9,10}. BDTC was synthesised¹¹ and purified by crystallisation from benzene. Spectrophotometric measurements were made with a Beckman DU2 spectrophotometer with optically matched quartz cells (1 cm). A Elico LI-10 pH meter was used for pH measurements.

Procedure: To a sample solution containing 50 µg of Ru^{III} or 97.55 µg of Pt^{IV} was added of 1.0×10^{-2} M BDTC solution (4 ml) in acetone. For Ru, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 2.0. For Pt^{IV}, 0.1 M stannous chloride solution (2 ml) was added and pH adjusted to 0.3. The solution was heated to 100° for 1 h on a water-bath and then allowed to cool and equilibrated by shaking for 15 min with chloroform (10 ml). The absorbance of the dry extracts were measured at 425 nm for Ru^{III} and 352 nm for Pt^{IV} using the reagent blank.

Results and Discussion

It was found that 80-fold and 30-fold molar excess of BDTC were necessary for complete extraction of Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV}, respectively. Same concentration of the reagent was maintained in the subsequent studies. The Ru^{III} and the Pt^{IV} complexes with BDTC gave same λ_{\max} in solvent, like benzene, toluene, *p*-xylene, cyclohexane, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide, but the absorbance values were different. Chloroform was found to be the best solvent as the complexes showed highest distribution ratio in it.

A minimum of 70 min heating time was required to develop the maximum colour intensity and the extracts were stable for at least 5 h at $27 \pm 2^\circ$. The period of equilibration was varied from 0.5 to 20 min and the extraction was found to be quantitative after 10 min. The complexes obey Beer's law upto 8.4 and 11.1 ppm of Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV}, respectively. The molar absorptivities of the Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} complexes were found to be 4.2×10^3 and 9.3×10^3 dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹, respectively. Sensitivities in term of Sandell's definition¹², were 0.023 8 µg cm⁻² Ru^{III} and 0.020 96 µg cm⁻² Pt^{IV}. Relative errors were $\pm 2.1\%$ for Ru^{III} and $\pm 1.1\%$ for Pt^{IV}.

Effect of foreign ions: Among the cations (added as chloride, nitrate or sulphate), 100-fold of Be^{II}, Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Sr^{II}, Ba^{II}, Cu^{II}, Rh^{III}, U^{VI}, Th^{IV} and alkali metal ions do not interfere. Ni^{II}, Zn^{II} and Pd^{II} interfere seriously in Ru^{III}; and Pd^{II}, Cd^{II}, Fe^{III} and Hg^{II} interfere seriously in Pt^{IV}. Among anions, 300-fold excess of acetate, tartarate, borate, molybdate, bromide, iodide, triocyanate (added as alkali metal salts) do not interfere. Tolerance limit of nitrite and fluoride ions are quite low in case of Pt^{IV}.

Stoichiometry and stability of complexes: The molar composition of Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} chelates of BDTC was determined by mole ratio method¹³ and Job's method¹⁴ of continuous variation. The two methods indicated the formation of 1:1 complex in either of the case. The log K values (K=stability constant) for Ru^{III} and Pt^{IV} complexes were found to be 4.8 ± 0.05 and 5.5 ± 0.05 , respectively.

Acknowledgement

Authors are thankful to the Head of the Department of Chemistry, Nagpur University, for facilities.

References

1. H. GARNIAK, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1975, **275**, 205.
2. H. S. GOWDA and P. G. RAMAPPA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1976, **45**, 218.
3. W. GEILMANN and R. NEEB, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1956, **152**, 96.
4. J. DAS and K. DATTA, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, **14**, 917.
5. J. T. PYLE and S. K. MAJUMDAR, *Anal. Chem.*, 1964, **39**, 1796.
6. A. I. BUSEV and A. N. SHISHKOV, *Natural*, 1970, **3**, 71.
7. S. GANGOPADAHYAY, P. K. GANGOPADHAYA and S. O. SHOMA, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **281**, 143.
8. S. B. GAWALI and V. M. SHINDE, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1976, **280**, 99.
9. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1961.
10. J. BRANDSTATER and J. VRSTAL, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Commun.*, 1961, **26**, 392, 1962, **27**, 1798.
11. M. AKBAR ALI and M. T. H. FARAFDAR, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 1785.
12. E. B. SANDELL, "Colorometric Determination of Traces of Metals", Intersciences, New York, 1959, p. 83.
13. J. H. YOE and A. L. JONES, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.
14. P. JOB, *Ann. Chim.*, 1928, **9**, 113.

Cation Exchange Chromatographic Separation of Nickel in Mixed Solvents

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Manuscript received 20 September 1985, revised 8 April 1986, accepted 23 April 1986

THE cation exchange chromatographic studies of nickel were attempted in mixed solvents¹⁻³ with hydrochloric acid. Nitric acid⁴ and hydrobromic acid⁵ were also used with methanol and acetone. Such methods were not selective as ions forming anionic complexes showed strong interferences. Thus work on the separation of less common elements from nickel was lacking. Such studies are reported in this paper.